

USE OF DIFFERENT METHODS AND APPROACHES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Nurmamatova Farangiz Irkinovna

Assistant teacher, Department of
“Humanitarian sciences and English”,
Fiscal institute under the State Tax Committee
of the Republic of Uzbekistan
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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this article is to provide an assessment of the role played by methods in education process, though there is also an account of the main different methods of foreign language teaching (FLT) that are in use today. For a teacher, methods prescribe what materials and activities should be used, how they should be used and what the role of the teacher and how it should be like in the classroom.

Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi ta'lim jarayonidagi usullarning rolini baholashdan iborat bo'lib, bugungi kunda chet tillarini o'qitishning qo'llaniladigan turli xil usullari haqida ma'lumot beradi. O'qituvchi uchun qanday uslub va metodlar, materiallar hamda mashg'ulotlardan foydalanish kerakligini, shu bilan birga o'qituvchining roli va sinfda qanday bo'lishi kerakligi haqida ham bir qancha foydali ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yondashuv, usullar, qoidalar, lingvistik, sotsiolingvistik tamoyillar, materiallar, faoliyat, o'qituvchining roli, texnika, o'quvchilar, amaliyot.

To start with, it is noticeable to mention that knowledge of different approaches gives foreign language teachers a proper background reference to their own stand on pedagogical matters and classroom practice, furthermore helps them to understand the importance of FLT in this century.

In foreign language teaching practice, there are different approaches and they differ in different countries as well as the types of approaches are used differently.

For a teacher, methods prescribe what materials and activities should be used, how they should be used and what the role of the teacher and how it should be like in the classroom. For learners, methods define what approach to learning the learner should take and what roles the learner should adopt in the classroom. All methods include prescriptions for the teacher and the learners. All methods are a pre-packaged set of specifications of how the teacher should teach and how the learner should learn derived from a particular theory of language and a theory of language learning.

An approach is the most abstract of all three concepts that refers to the linguistic, sociolinguistic principles underlying methods and techniques. For getting more information about what is approach it is beneficial to reckon about the following concerns, like what an approach is influenced by including the inquiry of what the theory of language is followed by

how the language is viewed. Additionally, concerning the question of how the learners learn the language, it is simply significant to bear in mind what the psychological and cognitive processes are involved such as habit formation, induction, inference or generalization. In all cases, what conditions need to be met for these learning processes should be activated. A technique is, on the other hand, the narrower of all these two; in fact, it is a just single produce to use in a kind of place. To illustrate, I would like to prove my sentences by the following graph:

In foreign language teaching practice, there are different approaches and they differ in different countries as well as the types of approaches are used differently. First of all, we have to analyze the types of approaches which are used by foreign teachers in other countries. As we looked at theoretical part, an approach is a theory of language teaching. According to William (2017:28), the theory of language underlying these methods is structural linguistics, and though there are some differences between British and American structuralism, both movements saw language as “a system of structurally related elements for the encoding of meaning, the elements being phonemes, 114 morphemes, words, structures, and sentence types”. After concluding this, it is understandable for us that Grammar is no more based on the collection of rules, as it consists of structures as well. Moreover, studying a language means to collect and analyzing all these steps of the language and rules to combine word with each other.

For instance, the main features are the importance part of oral aspects of the language, running out from the accordant of the written language. It is fact that, these conceptions appeared to offer a scientific basis for FLT, which are considered to have transformed teaching from an art into a science.

As for Arthur these were summarized in the following five ideas: 1. Language is a speech. 2. A language is what its native speakers say; it is not what someone thinks they ought to say. 3. Languages are different from each other's. 4. A language is a huge number of habits. 5. Teach the language, not about the language.

All choices are based on their theory of learning behavioristic habit – forming conceptions. All above-mentioned terms are currently in an active implementation both in foreign and local language teaching institutions in Uzbekistan, in the scope of communicative approach as it is an umbrella term to describe the methodology which teaches students how to communicate efficiently. It also emphasis on students responsibility for their own learning. It includes cooperating within group, self-activity and dictionary work. The first step of communicative approach is language acquisition rather than conscious learning. As for Krashen (2009:150) “acquisition is a natural process, similar to the way children develop ability in their first language a it is subconscious process when students are not aware of the fact, they are acquiring language but are using the language for communication”.

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